

Appendix G: Local continuum around 7 μm : Ced 110 IRS4A

A local continuum method is used to isolate the ice features between 7 and 10 μm in the MIRI/MRS spectrum of Ced 110 IRS4A. This methodology was first used by [Schutte et al. \(1999\)](#) to isolate the same ice features, and reproduced again in [Yang et al. \(2022\)](#). In [Rocha et al. \(2024\)](#) we used this method to analyse the ice features in the same spectral region as shown in this paper. The difference between this paper and [Rocha et al. \(2024\)](#) with previous works is that the local continuum is subtracted in optical depth scale after silicate removal and not with the spectrum in flux scale. This enhances the visibility of shallow ice features longwards of 8 μm . This method consists of tracing a fourth-order polynomial to guiding points anchored in the observational spectrum. The physical interpretation of this polynomial is that broad and strong solid-phase features of other components (e.g., NH_4^+ , H_2O ice bending mode, organic refractory material) can create a similar continuum that is similar to the polynomial profile.

Fig. G.1. Local continuum subtraction between 7 and 10 μm using a 4th order polynomial. Guiding points are anchored in the observational spectrum.

Appendix H: Statistical analysis and consistency checks

We derive the confidence intervals for the fits using the ENIIGMA fitting tool ([Rocha et al. 2021](#)). Briefly, the code explores how coefficient values in the linear combination changes the goodness of the fit. From this analysis, the code calculates χ^2 values for each new solutions and the confidence intervals are derived based on a $\Delta\chi^2$ map ([Avni & Bahcall 1980](#)), which is given by:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{1}{dof} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{\tau_{v,i}^{obs} - \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} w_j \tau_{v,j}^{lab}}{\gamma_{v,i}^{obs}} \right)^2, \quad (\text{H.1a})$$

$$\Delta\chi^2(\alpha, \epsilon) = \chi^2 - \chi_{min}^2, \quad (\text{H.1b})$$

where dof is the number of degrees of freedom, γ is the error in the observational optical depth spectrum propagated from the flux error assumed to be 5%, α and ϵ are the statistical significance and the number of free parameters, respectively. χ_{min}^2 corresponds to the goodness-of-fit in the global minimum solution.

Figures [H.1](#), [H.2](#), [H.3](#) and [H.4](#) show the confidence intervals analysis of Ced 110 IRS4A at 15.2 μm , 7 μm , 8–10 μm and for Ced 110 IRS4B between 2.5 and 5 μm , respectively. The lower and upper boundaries from these contours are used to derive the statistical error bars on the ice column densities presented in Table 3.

In addition to these analyses, we also perform consistency checks of the small spectral range fits. For example, in Figure [H.5](#) we overplot the same components used in the fit of the 7–10 μm range of Ced 110 IRS4A, but now covering the full spectral range between 2.5 and 25 μm . The goal of this approach is to assess whether the small range fit would over-predict the ice absorption in another spectral ranges. Similarly, in Figure [H.6](#), the components fitting the 2.5–5 μm data of Ced 110 IRS4B are compared to the observational data between 5 and 25 μm . For both sources, we conclude that the ENIIGMA fits are consistent with the full spectral range. We note that between 4 and 5 μm , where the CO_2 (CO stretch, 4.27 μm), CO (CO stretch, 4.67 μm) and OCN^- (CN stretch, 4.6 μm) ice bands are, no observational data is available.

Finally, we derive Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) values for the fit of the spectral range between 7 and 10 μm . AIC is a powerful statistical parameter to assess the quality of the fit because it adds a penalty to the χ^2 value when more parameters are included in the model. It can defined as:

$$AIC = \chi^2 + 2p + \frac{2p(p+a)}{N-p-1}, \quad (\text{H.2})$$

where p is the number of parameters and N is the number of bins. The ΔAIC is defined as $AIC_i - \min(AIC)$, where AIC_i represent values for different models, and $\min(AIC)$ corresponds to the minimum AIC value. The ΔAIC scores are interpreted as follows ([Burnham & Anderson 2002](#)):

Fig. H.1. Confidence interval analysis for the $15.2 \mu\text{m}$ band. Green, yellow and red contours indicate 1, 2, and 3σ confidence interval for a fit using four components.

Fig. H.2. Same as Figure H.1, but for the $7 \mu\text{m}$ band of Ced 110 IRS4A.

- $0 < \Delta\text{AIC} < 2$: substantial support of the model;
- $4 < \Delta\text{AIC} < 7$: considerably less support of the model;
- $\Delta\text{AIC} > 10$: essentially no support of the model.

Figure H.7 shows the ΔAIC value when more parameters are added to fit the $7\text{--}10 \mu\text{m}$ region. The lowest ΔAIC is reached when the eighth component is added to the mode, namely, N_2O . By adding SO_2 ($\text{CH}_3\text{OH}:\text{SO}_2$) and $\text{HCOOH}:\text{H}_2\text{O}:\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ the ΔAIC increases, which would lead to a weak support of the model. Nevertheless, adding SO_2 keeps the ΔAIC value in range of substantial

Fig. H.3. Same as Figure H.1, but for the 8–10 μm range of Ced 110 IRS4A.

support of the model. This is well aligned with the confidence interval analysis shown in Figure H.2, where SO_2 is not excluded in the 3σ confidence interval, whereas $\text{HCOOH:H}_2\text{O:CH}_3\text{OH}$ can be ruled out (Fig. H.3).

Figure H.8 displays both χ^2 and relative AIC values for different number of components in the fit. The χ^2 values remain the same for the fits with 5–7 components, which indicates that adding more IR spectra does not improve the fit. The AIC values allows the same conclusion. In addition, it shows that extra components to the fit increases the AIC values. Therefore, a fit with five components is ideal for Ced 110 IRS4A.

References

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Fig. H.4. Same as Figure H.1, but for the 2.5–5 μm range of Ced 110 IRS4B.

Fig. H.5. Consistency check for IRS4A: Sum of ice components fitting the range between 7–10 μm (Fig.10) compared to the full MIRI spectrum before and after continuum, silicate and H₂O ice subtraction.

Fig. H.6. Consistency check for IRS4B: Sum of ice components fitting the range between 2.5-5 μm (Fig. ??) compared to the full MIRI/MRS spectrum. Some PAH emission bands are indicated in this figure.

Fig. H.7. Relative Akaike Information Criterion for the fit between 7 and 10 μm . Coloured regions indicate the support to the model.

Fig. H.8. Relative Akaike Information Criterion and χ^2 for the fit of the CO₂ ice bending mode at 15.2 μm .